

EXERCISE TO PREVENT OF GESTATIONAL DIABETES MELLITUS IN PREGNANCY: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract

Background. Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM) is a pregnancy complication that is common in 3.5 to 12% of pregnancies. Pregnant women have a very high risk of developing diabetes due to an increase in blood sugar metabolism during pregnancy. Various meta-analyzes related to the effect of regular physical activity on reducing the incidence of GDM have been carried out, but there is evidence that needs significant influence to recommend a program of regular physical activity to prevent GDM incidents. So this study aims to examine the literature using the latest references on the effect of physical exercise in reducing the incidence of GDM. Method. systematic literature review with keywords; gestational diabetes mellitus, physical exercise, and pregnant women. Articles obtained from the electronic database "Google Scholar" with the criteria for inclusion of scientific articles in English and Indonesian in 2014-2024. Results. Several recent studies have shown regular physical activity exercises conducted 55-60 minutes for 3 times a week can reduce GDM and other things related to GDM namely a decrease in glycemic levels, blood pressure, and body weight. In addition, regular physical exercise can also improve fetal well-being as evidenced by an increase in the neonatal body index. Conclusion. Regular physical exercise shows enough evidence to reduce the risk of GDM. Recommendation. Regular physical activity is highly recommended to reduce the incidence of GDM. Although new evidence is needed that shows a significant effect on the decline in GDM. However regular physical exercise does not have a dangerous effect as long as it is done by pregnant women who are recommended.

Keywords : Diabetic Mellitus, Gestational, Preventive Exercises.

1. INTRODUCTION

Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM) is defined as a state of glucose intolerance that is absent or undetected before pregnancy. The prevalence of GDM continues to increase worldwide; 1 in 7 women in the world experience GDM, and 1-14% of all pregnancies in Indonesia experience GDM. Based on data from the IDF (International Diabetes Federation) in 2012, more than 300 million people worldwide have DM, and around 60 million of them are women of reproductive age (15-49 years)..

Pregnant women have a very high risk of developing diabetes due to increased blood sugar metabolism during pregnancy; in addition, women with excess body weight or obesity also have a very high risk of developing GDM. Hyperglycemia in mothers increases the risk of complications such as preeclampsia, hypertension, neonatal macrosomia, and even death.

Many interventions can be done to overcome diabetes problems in pregnant women, one of which is physical exercise. Currently, exercise is recommended as part of antenatal care. Exercise or physical activity can increase insulin sensitivity and also maintain blood sugar levels in patients with type 2 diabetes. A study shows a correlation between physical activity before and during pregnancy and lower GDM values. Physical activity can be given to pregnant women without contraindications. The duration of exercise is adjusted to the type of physical activity to be done. [1]

According to Wang's research [2] exercise is very influential in reducing blood sugar levels in pregnant women, with the results of blood sugar in the intervention group being significantly lower (22% vs. 40.6%, $P < 0.001$). These results are in line with Kotic's research [3] that the intervention group had lower postprandial glucose levels at the end of pregnancy ($p < 0.001$) and

there was no significant difference in fasting glucose levels. From three meta-analyses conducted by Han et al. [4], dan [5] , it was said that physical activity did not have a significant effect on reducing GDM, but a study conducted by Aune [6] said that there was a significant effect, but new studies were needed to strengthen the evidence of the effect of physical activity in reducing GDM.

Based on the above phenomenon, the author intends to conduct a systematic literature review. The general objective: to determine the effect of physical exercise on reducing the incidence of gestational diabetes mellitus. While the specific objectives are to determine several other impacts related to gestational diabetes mellitus, the types of physical exercise recommended, and the time and intensity of physical exercise recommended.

2. METHODOLOGY

The method used is a systematic literature keywords gestational diabetes mellitus, physical exercise, and pregnant women. Articles are obtained from the electronic database "Google Scholar" with the inclusion criteria of scientific articles in English and Indonesian published in 2014-2024. The collected literature is analyzed and synthesized into a recommendation.

3. RESULTS

The results of the systematic literature review obtained 10 articles from a total of 19,800 articles obtained from the results of the literature search based on keywords and inclusion criteria that were set. The 10 articles collected were in English and Indonesian. The articles obtained were studies with randomized controlled trial (RCT) and quasi-experimental designs. The research locations of the collected articles were carried out in 9 countries, namely China, Norway, the United States (US), Croatia, Spain, Ireland, Indonesia, Norway, and Egypt. The measurements observed included (1) maternal well-being: incidence of gestational diabetes mellitus, body weight, insulin resistance, blood pressure, postprandial blood glucose, fasting blood sugar, blood measurements, skin folds, complication rates during pregnancy and birth, need for pharmacological therapy, percentage of fat during pregnancy, exercise compliance, and exercise motivation. (2) infant well-being: APGAR score, infant body mass, ponderal index, and neonatal body index. The interventions given were physical exercise in the form of cycling, intense endurance, strength training, balance training, moderate aerobic exercise, and diabetes gymnastics. [7];[8] ; [9]; [10] ; [3]; [11]; [2]. Some other interventions use supervision from medical personnel [12] [3] and some are done independently at home with face-to-face (F2F) [1]. Participants continue to do Activity Daily Living (ADL) [2], receive antenatal care [1], and receive medical care in the form of insulin and dietary recommendations for pregnant women with diabetes mellitus [9].

The results of literature studies found that regular physical exercise in pregnant women can reduce the incidence of GDM [7]; [8]; [2] although a study by Daly [12] said the results did not have a significant effect. Other influences related to the incidence of GDM were observed, namely: body weight, insulin resistance, systolic blood pressure, postprandial blood glucose, and fasting blood glucose had a significant effect on reducing the measurement components [7]; [8] ; [3]; [1]; [2]. However, other studies say that body weight, diastolic blood pressure, and fasting glucose have no significant effect [13]; [8]; [3]. In the measurement of blood pressure conducted by Garnæs et al. [8], although the effect on systolic blood pressure is not significant, at the end of pregnancy there is a significant effect on the decrease or stability of systolic blood pressure ($p = 0.001$) and diastolic blood pressure ($p = 0.002$). In blood measurements, skin folds, maternal needs for pharmacological therapy, and maternal body fat presentation during pregnancy did not show a significant effect [8] [3]. The results of measurements related to fetal well-being, almost all components, did not show a significant effect. Only in neonatal body index measurements was there a significant effect size, while the APGAR score, infant body mass, and ponderal index did not show significant [3].

4. DISCUSSION

In this meta-analysis, regular physical exercise during pregnancy was associated with a significant reduction in the relative risk of GDM. There is sufficient evidence to suggest that physical exercise has a significant effect on reducing GDM. These results are in line with previous meta-analyses conducted by Aune et al [6] and in contrast to three meta-analyses in previous

years, which stated that there was insufficient evidence that physical exercise had a significant effect on reducing GDM in pregnant women; [4]; [5] .

Physical activity has benefits for pregnant women without complications, minimal risk, and is recommended in pregnancy guidelines. The results of several studies of physical activity during pregnancy can prevent GDM during pregnancy, especially for pregnant women with comorbidities and complications such as obesity. GDM is a common pregnancy complication in 3.5 to 12% of pregnancies [14]. Through physical activity can help control weight and reduce the risk of pregnancy in obese women. In women diagnosed with GDM, physical activity is useful in managing glycemic control. Managing glycemic control is important to reduce the adverse effects of uncontrolled GDM. [7]; [10]; [3].; [11]; [1]; [2].

These benefits greatly affect the well-being of the mother during pregnancy and the baby. In addition, other general benefits of physical activity include increased physical fitness [15] , reduced back pain [16]; [17], and reduced anxiety and depressive symptoms [7]. In addition to improving maternal well-being during pregnancy, physical activity during pregnancy can improve the well-being of the baby by increasing the neonatal body index [3]. So physical activity is highly recommended during pregnancy in pregnant women who are recommended for various reasons.

From the results of the literature study, it was found that the types of physical activity recommended during pregnancy to improve fitness and therapeutic benefits are cycling, moderate-intensity endurance training, strength training, brisk walking, aerobic exercise, and anti-diabetic gymnastics [7]; [10]; [3]; [11]; [1]; [2]. The recommended duration of physical activity for one exercise is, according to the protocol, namely 55-60 minutes [7]; [3]; [11]; [1]; [2], except for anti-diabetic gymnastics, which is done for 15-20 minutes, but there is no protocol regarding the time of exercise using anti-diabetic. The frequency of exercise for all types of exercise is 3 times per week [10]. However, antenatal care and insulin therapy are still needed for women with diabetes mellitus while carrying out a regular physical activity exercise program. In women diagnosed GDM, physical activity is beneficial in managing glycemic control. Managing glycemic control is important to reduce the adverse effects of uncontrolled GDM . These benefits greatly affect the well being of the mother during pregnancy and the baby, other general benefits of physical activity include improved physical fitness, reduced back pain, decreased anxiety and defressive symptoms

5. CONCLUSION

GDM is a common pregnancy complication that occurs in 3.5 to 12% of pregnancies. The results of literature studies show sufficient evidence to strengthen previous meta-analyses on the effect of regular physical exercise in reducing the incidence of GDM and other related matters. So far, meta-analyses conducted by various researchers and this meta-analysis show that regular physical activity is highly recommended to reduce the incidence of GDM. Although new evidence is needed to show the influence of GDM triggers, namely decreased blood sugar, weight, and blood pressure. In addition to improving maternal well-being during pregnancy, regular physical exercise also improves fetal well-being, as evidenced by a significant increase in neonatal body index to reduce GDM. However, regular physical exercise does not have a harmful effect as long as it is carried out by pregnant women as recommended. Physical exercise is recommended as part of antenatal care exercise or physical activity can improve insulin sensitivity and also maintain blood sugar levels in type 2 diabetes patients.

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